

GENOTYPE IMPUTATION AND POPULATION GENETICS TECHNIQUES IN GENOMIC DATA ANALYSIS

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(MS Received: 23.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:01.01.2024)

MS 3130

(RESEARCH PAPER IN VETERINARY AND ANIMAL SCIENCE,)

Abstract

The challenges and strategies related to animal genotyping, particularly in economically disadvantaged countries like India. Despite recent cost reductions in animal genotyping, significant barriers still exist for large-scale genotyping projects. The abstract suggests that low-density SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism) chips can be produced economically, with various strategies for marker selection to transition from high-density to low-density SNP arrays. TRES, a suite of algorithms and software for efficiently handling and analyzing large-scale genotype datasets. TRES uses techniques like Delta, pairwise FST (Fixation Index), and marker information content to rank SNPs based on their ability to differentiate between breeds. It employs both the Delta approach and FIFS (Frequent Item Feature Selection) to curate informative SNP subsets. Several studies are cited to illustrate the effectiveness of different strategies. The use of low-density SNP panels is demonstrated in various cases, including accurate parentage verification, breed assignment, and detecting population-informative markers. The significance of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and genotype imputation is also highlighted, including their role in dimensionality reduction, population structure analysis, and improving genotype data accuracy. Various software tools are discussed, such as BEAGLE and MINIMAC, which are utilized for genotype imputation from phased genotypes and reference panels. The abstract emphasizes that the choice of software, imputation strategy, and selection of animals for genotyping can significantly impact imputation accuracy.

Keywords: Plink, Haploview, Fifs, Structure, Pca, Beagle, Minimac

Introduction

While the expense associated with animal genotyping has reduced recently, it still poses a significant barrier to genotyping a considerable number of animals concurrently. This challenge is particularly pronounced in economically disadvantaged countries like India. It's important to highlight that economical low-density SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism) chips can be manufactured using diverse criteria, resulting in substantial cost reduction. Techniques such as the selection of markers that differentiate between breeds, opting for markers with high levels of polymorphism, relying on markers chosen based on linkage disequilibrium (LD) estimates, considering markers based on their position in the genome to ensure comprehensive coverage, or employing a combination of these approaches, constitute various methods to transition from high-density to low-density SNPs. Such pruning can be executed using a range of tools and R packages

Tres

Advancements in high-throughput genomic technologies have opened avenues for investigating vast arrays of single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs), ranging from thousands to even millions. However, the task of identifying a compact subset of SNPs with exceptional information content has become progressively challenging. Existing tools for locus prioritization have faced criticism for exhibiting upward biases in results (regarding the anticipated precision of the chosen marker set for population assignment), grappling with high-dimensional datasets, and demanding substantial computational resources in certain scenarios. Enter TRES—a suite of algorithms seamlessly integrated into intuitive and computationally efficient software capable of swiftly handling and analyzing datasets encompassing millions of genotypes (TRES User Guide, 2015).

TRES encompasses a variety of well-established techniques for appraising and ranking SNPs within user-defined populations, subsequently generating a roster of premier loci. Furthermore, the software includes algorithms for manipulating datasets, facilitating the conversion of data between diverse formats, partitioning initial datasets into training and testing subsets, and constructing datasets containing exclusively the chosen SNPs identified during the SNP selection analysis, these can later be assessed using specialized software such as GENECLASS. This program serves as a valuable asset for biologists aiming to identify loci that offer maximum efficacy for constructing cost-effective panels. These panels find

utility in applications like species identification, wildlife management, and forensic inquiries (Kavakiotis et al., 2015). TRES primarily employs three criteria—Delta, pairwise FST, and marker information content—to rank SNPs based on their ability to discriminate between breeds.

Delta

In the context of a biallelic marker, the Delta value is determined using the equation: $\delta = |p_{iA} - p_{jA}|$ Here, p_{iA} represents the frequency of allele A in the i th population, while p_{jA} represents the frequency of the same allele A in the j th population. The calculation of the Delta value is restricted to comparisons between two populations. In situations involving more than two populations, the Delta value is computed as the average of the Delta values across all conceivable combinations of existing populations.

Wright's Fixation Index

When considering the Delta approach, the FST value for a biallelic marker is calculated using the subsequent equation:

Where: H_s stands for the average anticipated heterozygosity across subpopulations. H_t represents the anticipated heterozygosity of the entire population.

This methodology hinges on evaluating the discriminatory potency of SNPs concerning breed differentiation, grounded in FST estimations.

FIFS: Frequent Item Feature Selection

Introducing a distinctive data mining approach named FIFS (Frequent Item Feature Selection), designed to refine informative markers from SNP chips. FIFS adeptly extracts valuable markers from vast SNP genomic datasets through the utilization of frequent items. This modular methodology comprises two core components. In the first step, for each sampled population, it identifies the most prevalent and unique genotypes. Subsequently, the second component judiciously selects the optimal choices from these genotypes to construct the informative SNP subsets that will be employed. Notably, FIFS surpasses prior techniques in performance, furnishing scientists with the ability to cherry-pick the most informative markers characterized by exceptional discrimination power. These selected markers facilitate cost-effective panel optimization with wide-ranging applications including species identification, wildlife management, and forensics.

In numerous instances, FIFS substantially elevates the effectiveness of preceding methodologies, culminating in heightened accuracy in assignments. The significance of feature selection for SNP datasets is irrefutable, evident across both biological research and machine

learning. The pertinence of feature selection, encompassing the curation of SNPs with maximal information content, has been underscored in diverse research ventures. This emphasis originates from both a biological perspective and the economic constraints of producing comprehensive genome-wide data. Consequently, the adoption of smaller panels, or datasets, emerges as a pragmatic alternative—swift, economical, and versatile, these panels enable the genotyping of numerous individuals at a fraction of the expense associated with full genome-wide genotyping.

Vergara *et al.* (2014) shed light on the pertinent issues warranting the implementation of feature selection techniques. They provide a comprehensive exposition on feature selection methods, elucidating the state-of-the-art, and incorporating a mutual information feature selection framework into their study.

According to Getachew *et al.* (2017), the Ovine 50KSNP array proves itself as a powerful tool for discerning minor groupings of Ancestry Informative Markers (AIMs) in admixture studies. This array, containing 45 AIMs, facilitates reliable estimation of admixture levels. The authors highlight the potential market advantage that farmers could gain from readily accessible admixture estimation services utilizing these low-cost SNP chips, negating the reliance on incomplete or potentially flawed pedigree information.

Kavakiotis *et al.* (2017) conducted a study involving a dataset of 446 individuals grouped into 14 sub-populations. These individuals were genotyped across 59,436 SNPs, focusing on pig breed types within the United Kingdom. The researchers concluded that the FIFS approach can outperform the 95% assignment accuracy threshold while employing merely half the number of SNPs. Notably superior to alternative methods, FIFS assists biologists in the selection of the most informative markers, possessing the highest discrimination power, thereby optimizing cost-effectiveness.

Tortereau *et al.* (2017) crafted an SNP panel enabling dependable parentage assignment across a substantial portion of French sheep breeds. This panel's creation involved the genotyping of approximately 30 individuals from 27 and 3 populations, utilizing the 600 K and 54 K SNP chips, respectively. Demonstrating a minimum assignment rate of 94%, the panel's selected 249 SNPs were effectively tested for parentage attribution within the BMC breed. Presently, several French breeds are actively utilizing this panel.

In a study by Raoul *et al.* (2017), a comparison between classical and genomic selection strategies was undertaken using a stochastic model. The researchers explored five distinct genomic scenarios, involving alterations to the reference population structure, genotyping of females, and varying genotyping panel densities (ranging from medium density to imputed medium density from very low density). Genomic scenarios displayed heightened genetic gain and reduced inbreeding when juxtaposed with the traditional approach incorporating progeny testing. The effectiveness of the genomic scenarios stemmed from stronger selection differentials applied to male candidates in both artificial insemination (AI) and natural mating for sire selection. However, the usage of very low-density genotypes for male candidates and dams, combined with imputation, led to comparatively lower genetic gain than scenarios utilizing medium-density genotypes.

It serves as a valuable marker selection strategy specifically designed for the detection of Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) that contribute to the differentiation of underlying populations. The Population Specific Most Frequent Genotype Identification component within the FIFS approach draws inspiration from frequent item-set theory, pinpointing the feature space associated with SNPs possessing unique genotypes. In contrast, the Informative Marker Subset Construction component works to curate subsets of SNPs. The initial step of the algorithm involves identifying the feature space and retaining SNPs exhibiting a high frequency of values/genotypes within a single population (Eastaff and Saravanan, 2018).

In their study, Paim *et al.* (2019) centered their attention on 18 single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) aimed at distinguishing Brazilian

Crioula, Morada Nova (MN), and Santa Inês (SI) sheep breeds. Analysing data from 588 animals, they revealed that while this set of 18 SNPs exhibited a high level of reliability, it remained insufficient for definitively assigning the researched breeds, which are predominantly hair breeds. For a broader application in breed assignment, the development of a more refined panel is still necessary.

The use of Random Forest (RF) for identifying population-informative markers resulting from high-throughput genotyping technologies was brought to light by Schiavo *et al.* (2020). By utilizing RF selection algorithms, they successfully identified informative SNPs that evaded detection by other conventional methods such as Delta, Fst, and PCA. This distinct success can potentially be attributed to the inherent qualities of machine learning methodologies, particularly their aptitude for identifying and utilizing information about SNP interdependencies and interactions. These attributes can lead to substantial gains, especially in cases where non-linear class boundaries come into play. The prospect of using RF methods to uncover selection signature regions that encapsulate population-specific traits unaddressed by alternative methods is a compelling avenue for future exploration.

In their work, Berry *et al.* (2019) employed a low-density panel of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) to construct SNP panels comprising 87 to 500 SNPs for accurate parentage verification and discovery in a population of 9,390 purebred sheep. They adopted an exclusion and likelihood-based methodology for parentage verification and discovery. When the objective was to definitively identify the true sire or dam from all possible candidates, a minimum of 350 SNPs was deemed essential through exclusion, allowing for discordant offspring-parent genotype pairs. Furthermore, their findings indicated that for genome-wide SNP selection, a minimum of 250 meticulously chosen SNPs would be required to confirm that the most likely selected parent based on the probability approach was indeed the true parent.

Marina *et al.* (2020) delved into the challenge of transitioning from multiallelic microsatellites to biallelic markers (SNPs) for pedigree variation analysis in sheep. They unveiled the effectiveness of using a flanking 2 Mb SNP window for each microsatellite, which demonstrated high imputation accuracy. This not only offered breeders a cost-effective, low-density SNP chip but also enabled individual identification and parentage verification, minimizing the need for redundant genotyping.

Gebrehiwot *et al.* (2021) concluded that when dealing with compact SNP panels to calculate breed ancestries, priority should be given to SNPs that effectively distinguish closely related ancestral populations. This becomes crucial when the selection of SNP panels is constrained, as illustrated in a comparison involving 38 k versus 713 k SNPs. They posited that a single panel comprising 300 to 500 SNPs could deliver accurate estimations of exotic dairy fraction in various crossbred populations, given the shared ancestral background. Additionally, they proposed a marker panel encompassing at least 200 SNPs for estimating breed proportion (70 percent AFTvsEUT) and determining parentage (MAF-East). This strategy proves particularly beneficial in scenarios where pedigree information is scant or absent, enabling swift and cost-effective predictions of total dairy breed proportion and parentage verification within African crossbred cow populations. This approach in turn optimizes crossbreeding and ongoing genetic enhancement efforts.

Principal Component Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) stands as a method for dimensional reduction that ensures orthogonal evaluations of correlated variables. This approach involves computing principal components and utilizing them to transform the data's basis. In some cases, only the initial principal components are calculated, discarding the remaining components. PCA finds application in exploratory data analysis and the development of predictive models. It is commonly employed for dimensionality reduction, where data points are

projected onto the first few principal components, achieving lower-dimensional data representation while retaining maximal variance.

According to Menozzi *et al.* (1978), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a technique designed to linearly reduce the dimensions of intricate datasets. Through this transformation, the initial vector of correlated variables is converted into a vector of uncorrelated principal components. These primary components enable the determination of most of the variance among populations and individuals. The first principal component can be understood as the direction that maximizes the expected variance within the data (Jolliffe and Cadima, 2016). However, PCA might not capture the entirety of variation, necessitating the use of other multivariate analytical methods for comprehensive genome-wide SNP data analysis.

Genome-wide Complex Trait Analysis (GCTA) Program: The GCTA program was developed by Yang and colleagues at Peter Visscher's group at the University of Queensland to address the challenge of "missing heritability." Unlike assessing the relationship of each individual SNP with a complex trait, GCTA estimates the variance explained by all SNPs on a chromosome or across the entire genome. This tool involves data management, estimating genetic associations from SNPs, conducting mixed linear model analyses of variance explained by SNPs, estimating linkage disequilibrium structure, and simulating GWAS data. The GCTA program proves powerful for estimating and partitioning variation in complex traits using large GWAS datasets (Yang *et al.*, 2011). It also facilitates the formulation of genomic relationship matrices and conducting PCA on genome-wide SNP data.

GCTA is designed to estimate the proportion of phenotypic variance attributed to genome- or chromosome-wide SNPs for complex traits. The following functionalities are currently supported by GCTA:

Estimating genetic relationships from genome-wide SNPs, estimating inbreeding coefficients from genome-wide SNPs, estimating variance explained by all autosomal SNPs, partitioning genetic variance onto individual chromosomes, estimating genetic variance associated with the X-chromosome, testing dosage compensation effects on genetic variance on the X-chromosome, predicting genome-wide additive genetic effects for individual subjects and SNPs, estimating LD structure for a list of target SNPs, simulating GWAS data based on observed genotype data, converting Illumina raw genotype data into PLINK format, , conducting conditional and joint analysis of GWAS summary statistics without individual-level genotype data, conducting conditional and joint analysis of GWAS summary statistics without individual-level genotype data.

In a study by McTavish *et al.* (2012), the first principal component (PC) accounted for 13% of overall variability and distinguished between indicine and taurine breeds. Meanwhile, the PC2 gene was linked to the differentiation of European and African taurine breeds, explaining 3.2% of the overall changes.

Weerasingh *et al.* (2013) employed PCA and admixture analysis on East African smallholder dairy cattle using a 770K SNP beadchip. The initial five principal components accounted for approximately 92% of the variation. However, a low correlation of only 0.4% was observed between farmer assumptions and actual breed composition. **SNP Discriminative Power and Breed Assignment** The concept of Discriminant Analysis of Principal Components (DAPC) was pioneered by Jombart and colleagues (Jombart *et al.*, 2010) and serves as a tool for inferring the number of clusters comprising genetically related individuals. This multivariate statistical approach involves the partitioning of sample variance into between-group and within-group components, with the aim of maximizing discrimination between groups while minimizing it within groups. DAPC employs a two-step process: initially, data undergoes transformation via Principal Components Analysis (PCA), and subsequently, clusters are identified through Discriminant Analysis (DA). Execution of the DAPC methodology can be accomplished within the R programming environment using the 'adegenet' package.

DAPC serves as a multivariate technique designed to detect and describe clusters of genetically linked individuals. In cases where group priors are absent, DAPC utilizes sequential K-means and model selection to deduce genetic clusters.

Adegenet

Adegenet, as highlighted by Jombart and Ahmed (2011), is an R-package designed for the comprehensive exploration of genetic data. It encompasses a range of tools spanning multivariate techniques to spatial genetics and genome-wide SNP data analysis. The primary attributes of the 'adegenet' package include:

Data representation (classes) suitable for multivariate analysis. Importing data from GENETIX, STRUCTURE, Genepop, Fstat, EasyPop, or any genotype dataframe. Importing data from aligned DNA sequences to SNPs. Importing data from aligned protein sequences to polymorphic sites. Exporting data to R packages genetics, hierfstat, LDheatmap. Handling various levels of ploidy. Managing codominant markers and presence/absence data. Fundamental and advanced data manipulation. Basic data information (heterozygosity, allele counts, sample sizes, etc.). Computation of genetic distances, hybridization simulation. Spatial genetics methods: sPCA, global and local structuring tests, Monmonier algorithm. Seq Track algorithm for haplotype genealogy reconstruction. Simulation of haplotype genealogies, Discriminant Analysis of Principal Components (DAPC), efficient handling and analysis of genome-wide SNP data, Extracting SNPs from genomic alignments, graph-based clustering of genomic data, identifying mutations between sequence pairs. visualizing SNP density and testing randomness of distribution, web interface for DAPC, featuring selection and cross-validation, rapid maximum-likelihood clustering and hybrid identification using snapclust, exporting multivariate analysis outcomes for geographic mapping using mvmapper.

Genotype Imputation

Genotype imputation is an essential tool in the analysis of genome wide association scans. The technique allows geneticists to accurately evaluate the evidence for association at genetic markers that are not directly connected to genotyped. Genotype imputation particularly uses for combining the association scan results across studies that rely on different genotyping platforms. It can be used for short stretches of shared haplotype to estimate the effects of many variants that are not directly genotyped with great precision (Yun *et al.*, 2009). Genotype imputation is based on identity by descent (IBD). Two chromosome segments that are inherited from a common ancestor without recombination since the common ancestor are said to be inherited identical by descent. In an IBD segment, the two chromosomes will have identical allele sequences except at sites that have mutated in one of the lineages since the common ancestor. We can use the genotypes at the target markers to identify long IBD segments that a target haplotype shares with the reference haplotypes. If an IBD segment is accurately identified, the ungenotyped alleles in the IBD segment in the target haplotype can be copied from the IBD segment in the reference haplotype. Since there is uncertainty in inferring IBD, a probabilistic model is used to account for the uncertainty and to produce a posterior probability for each possible allele at an imputed marker on the target haplotype. This probabilistic model is typically a hidden Markov model (HMM) (Rabiner, 1989). Imputation may single out an untyped SNP as having the strongest signal of association in a given region, with implications for the follow-up strategy. Imputation should assist with the reconstruction of lacking genotypes in untyped participants in pedigreed data (Ellinghaus *et al.*, 2009). The computations that underlie genotype imputation are based on a haplotype reference; the available haplotype reference data that are provided by the International HapMap Project are usually employed (The International HapMap Consortium, 2003; The International HapMap Consortium, 2005). Different software's are available for imputation of genotyping data from missing or untyped data. These software's include BEAGLE, MINIMAC, MaCH and FIMPUTE, etc. and work on different

underlying principles. Phasing the genotypes may be one of the requirements before imputation process.

Beagle

BEAGLE, a genetic analysis software package written in Java, encompasses tools for haplotype and missing-data inference, single-marker and multilocus association analysis, as well as permutation testing (Browning and Browning, 2007). The software employs its proprietary genotype data format but offers Java utilities to facilitate the conversion of phased and unphased data files from the QTDT format. Operating platform-independent in Java, BEAGLE utilizes discrete genotype input format and generates posterior probability output format. Allelic R square serves as the quality metric for BEAGLE's imputation, with Chromosome being the target of imputation. A distinctive feature of BEAGLE is its capability to handle multi-allelic markers (Browning and Browning, 2007).

According to Ellinghaus et al. (2009), BEAGLE is marginally less precise than FIMPUTE and MaCH, yet it stands out as the fastest and well-documented option, especially for multi-allelic markers. One of BEAGLE's strengths is its adaptability to process offspring-parent trio and offspring-parent pair data independently or in conjunction with phased or unphased data of unrelated individuals. BEAGLE accommodates markers with up to 128 different alleles, and its computational runtime is influenced by the combined size of the sample and the reference panel (Browning et al., 2009).

Weng et al. (2013) conducted a study comparing the efficiency of three widely used imputation algorithms (fast PHASE, BEAGLE, and find hap) using Chinese Holstein cattle with Illumina BovineSNP50 genotypes. By evaluating different reference population sizes, they found that BEAGLE exhibited the best performance and robustness, achieving imputation accuracies exceeding 90% in nearly all scenarios. BEAGLE has shown reliability in imputing genotypes across varying genotyping platform densities, from low to high density.

In a study by Ventura et al. (2016), version 3.3.2 of BEAGLE was selected to assess imputation accuracy using different SNP panel densities in a multi-breed sheep population. The findings highlighted that imputation accuracy in sheep breeds can be enhanced through SNP panels, software choices, imputation strategies (one- or two-step), and judicious selection of animals to be genotyped using both high- and low-density SNP panels.

Korkuc et al. (2019) performed a comparison of imputation tools BEAGLE and MINIMAC to determine the optimal imputation strategy for a small cattle population. Their study suggested that BEAGLE outperformed with unphased target populations and larger reference panels.

MINIMAC

MINIMAC presents a memory-efficient and computationally streamlined implementation of the MaCH algorithm, tailored for genotype imputation. Built to operate on phased genotypes, it excels at handling extensive reference panels with numerous haplotypes. The name "MINIMAC" comprises two parts: "mini," signifying its demand for modest computational resources, and "mac," an abbreviation for MaCH, the widely used genotype imputation algorithm. The current version offers two options: minimac and minimac-omp. The latter incorporates OpenMP protocol, enabling

multi-threading for enhanced throughput (Howie et al., 2012; Fuchsberger et al., 2014).

Ventura et al. (2016) made noteworthy observations on improving imputation accuracy in sheep breeds through specific recommendations related to SNP panels, software choices, imputation strategies (one- or two-step), and even the selection of animals for genotyping using both high- and low-density SNP panels. When comparing imputation from 5K to HD to imputation from 5K to 50K, a slight enhancement (0.6%) was seen in the former. The study also explored imputation accuracy loss for SNPs at chromosome ends, revealing that only chromosome 26 exhibited overall imputation (5K to 50K) accuracy above 60% for 100 SNPs at each end (r^2).

Bolormaa et al. (2019) achieved a mean imputation accuracy of up to 0.97 for whole genome sequence across target breeds using Minimac3 software, with pre-phasing facilitated by Eagle software and variant filtering based on Minimac3 R2 exceeding 0.4. Their findings showcased improved imputation accuracy through amalgamation of smaller breed sets into a multi-breed reference. The accuracy of imputed WGS was assessed with Impute and Minimac3 software, starting from high-density (HD: ~500,000) SNP genotypes or low-density SNP genotypes (OvineLD: 12 k SNPs).

Schiavo et al. (2020) employed PLINK to identify Tag SNPs from the filtered SNP dataset for each breed, focusing on SNPs with $r^2 < 0.3$ with any other SNPs within breed. They retained non-redundant SNPs, tagging a group within each breed with a randomly chosen SNP. The study's approach started with the reduction of redundancy within the SNP panel, considering only SNPs not in high LD. This initial pre-selection enabled the application of a machine learning approach to the remaining dataset, which was reduced to about 1/5 of the untagged SNP panel. This process aimed to select informative SNPs for discriminating pigs of seven breeds.

Fernandes Júnior et al. (2021) investigated imputation accuracy to whole-genome sequences in Nellore cattle, utilizing FImpute3 and MINIMAC4. They concluded that Eagle-Minimac4 combination achieved higher accuracy for common variants, while FImpute3 exhibited superior computational efficiency and imputation accuracy for low-frequency variants.

Statistical and Bioinformatics Tools: The emergence of high-density SNP BeadChips for various livestock species has underscored the need for innovative approaches to manage vast genotypic data. In pursuit of novel analytical methods for such extensive genotypic information, a range of tools spanning statistical and bioinformatics domains have been developed over time. These tools play a pivotal role in estimating ancestry levels within individuals of mixed populations, facilitating the inference of average ancestry levels across populations. Some programs aid in population stratification by transforming non-linear variation data into linear formats, thereby elucidating underlying variations. Additionally, certain tools enable the estimation of population parameters related to genetic diversity and population structure. While some tools encompass the entire spectrum of tasks, including analyzing admixture levels, genetic diversity, and population structure, others may focus on specific aspects. The analysis of raw outcomes generated by these tools is of paramount importance, as raw data holds value only when it is meticulously analysed and interpreted.

Table No. 1: Different tools (Bioinformatics and Statistical) used and their purposes

S. No.	Program /Tools	Latest Version	Properties/use/ purpose	Reference
01	PLINK	v1.07	A plink tutorial we will consider using plink to analyses example data, using plink to work with the data, using a range of feature: data management, summary statistic, population stratification and basic association analysis Plink facilitates the manipulation and analysis of whole genome datasets and helps in population stratification through IBS and IBD analysis. Besides providing various ways to prune and process the datasets for quality control parameters, it also helps in	https://zzz.bwh.harvard.edu/plink/tutorial.shtml (Purcell et al., 2007)

merging and LD-based pruning of datasets as per the commands employed by the researcher.

02	Haploview		Haploview is designed to simplify and expedite the process of haplotype analysis by providing a common interface to several tasks relating to such analysis. It can analyze thousands of SNPs in thousands of individuals. Haploview is open-source project hosted by source Forge.	Barrett <i>et al.</i> (2005) Wigginton <i>et al.</i> (2005)
03	FIFS		FIFS - Frequent Item Feature Selection, is a novel data mining approach, which is based on the notion of frequent items for selecting the most informative markers from population genomic data. It is implemented in Java and therefore can be executed in all operating systems. After navigating to the root folder of the executable you can run the executable via command prompt or terminal. It achieves accuracy of 95% needing half the number of SNPs selected by other methods.	http://intelligence.cs.dtu.dk/~bioinformatics/fifs/ Kavakiotis <i>et al.</i> (2017)
04	STRUCTURE	Version 2.3.4	The program STRUCTURE is used for assigning individuals to distinct populations, studying hybrid zones and estimating the allele frequencies in admixed populations. It probabilistically works out the members of the dataset to K sub-populations based on a Bayesian statistical approach using Markov Chain Monte-Carlo method (MCMC). It can be applied to most of the commonly-used genetic markers, including SNPs, microsatellites, RFLPs and AFLPs.	Pritchard <i>et al.</i> (2000); Falush <i>et al.</i> (2003)
05	Principal Component Analysis (PCA)		PCA is mainly used to account for population-specific variations in alleles distribution on the SNPs (or other DNA markers) under investigation. Such “population substructure” mainly arises as a consequence of varying frequencies of minor alleles in genetically distant ancestries. It reduces the multi-dimensionality of variations in datasets to linear dimensionality and helps to explain the variation among the members of dataset/population based on linear components of variation.	
06.	BEAGLE	3.0.2	BEAGLE make use of a localised haplotype-cluster model and it is a software package for phasing genotypes and for imputing ungenotyped.	Ellinghaus <i>et al.</i> (2009)
07.	MINIMAC	Minimac4, version 1.0.0	It is a low memory, computationally efficient implementation of the MaCH algorithm for genotype imputation. It is designed to work on phased genotypes and can handle very large reference panels with hundreds or thousands of haplotypes.	Howie <i>et al.</i> (2012); Fuchsberger <i>et al.</i> (2014)

Conclusion

In conclusion, the realm of genomics has undergone remarkable progress, empowering researchers to explore the nuances of genetic diversity, population dynamics, and breed identification within livestock species. The cost reduction associated with animal genotyping has played a pivotal role in extending this exploration to larger population scales. However, economic constraints persist, particularly in countries like India, underscoring the practicality of transitioning from high-density to low-density SNP panels. In pursuit of this goal, diverse methodologies have emerged, centered around marker curation, identification of informative SNPs, and the optimization of cost-effective genotyping arrays. TRES, a suite of algorithms, stands out as a formidable asset for SNP prioritization, ranking, and optimization. By harnessing techniques like Delta, FST, and marker information content, TRES excels in pinpointing markers with exceptional discriminatory power. Augmented by Frequent Item Feature Selection (FIFS), it enhances breed assignment accuracy and population differentiation, serving as an indispensable tool across applications ranging from species authentication to forensic investigations. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) retains its significance as a potent approach for unravelling population substructure and comprehending variance in allele distribution among diverse lineages. This method helps mitigate challenges posed by population-specific variations, contributing to a deeper grasp of genetic diversity. Genotype imputation, facilitated by tools like

BEAGLE and MINIMAC, assumes a pivotal role in analyzing genome-wide association scans and harmonizing outcomes across distinct genotyping platforms. Imputation proves critical for accurately evaluating genetic markers not directly captured through genotyping, thus enriching our understanding of intricate genetic traits. The fusion of statistical and bioinformatics tools has enabled the manipulation and analysis of expansive genotypic datasets, leading to revelations in population genetics, ancestry elucidation, and breed identification. These tools, coupled with the ever-evolving landscape of genomic technologies, beckon promising avenues for further untangling the complexities of genetic diversity within livestock species. Consequently, they contribute substantively to the advancement of breeding tactics, animal husbandry, and conservation initiatives.

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